

THE COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS AND GLYCERIDES OF THE SEED FAT OF *MANGIFERA INDICA* (MANGO)*

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Component fatty acids and glyceride structure of the seed fat of *Mangifera Indica* have been studied. The fatty acids comprise myristic (0.89%), palmitic 8.83%, stearic (33.96%), arachidic (6.74%) and oleic (49.78%). Mango fat comprises fully saturated glycerides (14.2%), mono-oleo-glycerides (24.2%), di-oleoglycerides (60.8%) and tri-unsaturated (0.8%).

Mangifera Indica (N. O. Anacardiaceae), commonly known as mango, is a large tree, indigenous to India and occurs almost every where on the plains and extensively cultivated for its fruits.

In general, there are two types of mango trees, one of which is grown from the seed, called "Tukhmi" and the other grown by grafting called "Kalmi". There are, however, several varieties in mango, each one differing from the other in size, colour, taste and flavour.

The kernel of the seed, which is grey-white in colour, contains about 12% of solid fat. No analytical data about the component fatty acids of the fat etc., are available except a few characteristics which were determined long ago by Peckolt (*Ber. phar. Ges.*, 1898, 8, 167), Jumelle ("les Huilles vegetable", 1921) and Sack (*Pharm. Weekbl.*, 1911, 13; *Apoth. Z.*, 1911, 26, 362) are given below:—

Butyro No at 48°	48.4
Acid value	12.3
Saponification value	175.0
Iodine value	30.0 to 54.5
R.M value	0.2

With a view to studying quantitatively the component fatty acids, as well as the glyceride structure of the fat and also to see if it can be commercially exploitable, the present study was undertaken.

Methods of analysis, as developed by Hilditch and his collaborators, have been followed.

EXPERIMENTAL

For the present study kernels from the mangoes of a tree of *Tukhmi* variety were taken. The kernels were well dried, powdered and extracted with carbon tetrachloride in a Soxhlet's extractor.

6.5 Kg. of the kernels thus extracted gave 662 g. of a solid fat (11.8%) having an acid value of 20.1 and m.p. 40.5°. Since the glyceride structure was to be studied, the fat was washed with a 10% solution of potassium carbonate to remove the free fatty acid present. The neutral fat so obtained has the following characteristics.

* This work has been carried out by S. P. Pathak to form a part of his thesis for the degree of Doctor of Science of the Benares Hindu University.

Colour	Greyish white	Sapon. value	194.8
Sp. gr. at 36°	0.9139	Iodine value	39.2
Butyro No. at 40°	51.5	R. M. value	0.13
Refractive index at 40°	1.4604	Hehner value	95.7
Acid value	0.28	Unsaponifiable matter	2.87%

Component Acids

For the estimation of the component fatty acids, 100 g. of the neutral fat were hydrolysed and the recovered fatty acids (95.7 g.) were then separated into "Solid" (53.56%) and "Liquid" (46.44%) acids by crystallising their lead salts from alcohol according to the modified Twitchell method (Hilditch *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1929, 23, 327). Each group of the acids was then converted into the corresponding methyl esters which were fractionally distilled from a Willstätter bulb under vacuum (0.5—1.00 mm.). Saponification equivalents and iodine values of each of the fractions were determined. The individual fractions were further analysed for the identification of the acids present therein. The fractionation data are given in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

Methyl esters of solid acids "S" (whole fat)

S.E. = 299.2. I.V. = 11.53.

Fraction No.	Wt.	B.p.	I.V.	S.E.
S ₁	3.30 g.	140-160°	8.51	278.5
S ₂	4.65	160-165°	8.70	286.4
S ₃	4.44	165-170°	8.90	290.4
S ₄	4.06	170-172°	9.42	292.5
S ₅	4.82	172-173°	10.10	295.8
S ₆	7.35	173-165°	10.20	299.7
S ₇	7.50	165-155°	9.40	302.8
S ₈	5.32	155-falling	8.7	305.6
S ₉	4.95	Residue	19.4	..
Total	46.39			

TABLE II

Methyl esters of liquid acids "L" (whole fat)

S.E. = 294.3. I.V. = 72.9

Fraction No.	Wt.	B.p.	I.V.	S.E.
L ₁	3.00 g.	120-153°	68.6	285.2
L ₂	3.42	153-155°	72.8	290.0
L ₃	4.49	155-160°	76.9	292.8
L ₄	5.00	160-162°	83.9	295.4
L ₅	4.47	162-163°	84.9	296.1
L ₆	3.98	163-falling	82.6	296.8
L ₇	6.45	Residue	75.9	300.4
Total	30.81			

Qualitative Examination of Individual Fractions

S₁.—Acids obtained from this fraction melted at 55°. After recrystallisation of the acids from acetone, the melting point rose to 63°. On recrystallisation the melting point did not change. When mixed with pure palmitic acid, the melting point was lowered only to 62.8°. It is therefore concluded that no acid lower than palmitic is present.

S₂.—Acids from this fraction melted at 62°. After crystallisation of the acid from 94% alcohol the sample melted at 70.5°. Recrystallisation from the same solvent had no effect on the melting point. The sample when mixed with pure stearic acid melted at 70.1°. It is obvious that the fraction contains stearic acid.

S₃.—Acids from this fraction melted at 71°. After crystallisation from 94% alcohol the melting point rose to 75°. Further crystallisation had no effect on the melting point. The mixed melting point could not be taken, as a pure sample of arachidic acid was not available. The mean molecular weight was found to be 312.2, indicating the presence of arachidic and or other higher acids.

S₄.—The unsaponifiable matter from the soap solution of the residual fraction was removed by ether. The fatty acids liberated had S.E. 295.5 and I.V. 12.40 and melting point 55°. After crystallising from alcohol the melting point was 61°. On further crystallisation the melting point rose to 68°, which did not change on further crystallisation. (It may be a mixture of oleic, stearic and arachidic acids).

Fractions L₄, L₅ and L₆ were combined and acids recovered. 3.5 G. of the recovered acids were dissolved in about 40 c.c. of anhydrous ether. The solution was kept in a freezing mixture and bromine slowly added till distinctly red. After keeping the mixture for four hours at -5° to -10°, no precipitate was observed to occur. Then the excess of bromine in the solution was removed by washing with sodium bisulphite. Bromo-adducts soluble in ether were recovered and dissolved in light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) and crystallised at 0°. No precipitate was formed, indicating thereby the absence of linoleic and linolenic acids, since these form insoluble bromo-additive products. The only unsaturated acid present, therefore, is oleic acid.

With the help of the above data, the component fatty acids of the mango fat have been calculated as given in Table III.

TABLE III

Component fatty acids of mango seed fat

Acids.	Solids (53.56%)	Liquids (46.44%)	Total (100)	Fatty acids (Wt. %)	Ex. N-8 (Mol. %)
Myristic	..	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.55
Palmitic	6.86	1.94	8.80	8.83	9.71
Stearic	33.87	..	33.87	33.96	33.66
As. arachidic	6.72	..	6.72	6.74	6.08
Oleic	5.99	43.67	49.66	49.78	49.70
Unsaponifiable	0.12	0.14	0.26

Glyceride Structure

For the estimation of glyceride structure, the neutralised fat was first separated by systematic crystallisation from acetone into three fractions, (A) least soluble, (B) medium soluble and (C) most soluble. Each fraction was then analysed for the component fatty acids by the ester-fractionation method, in the same way as the analysis of the whole fat was done. Fully saturated glycerides of the whole fat were also determined by the acetone permanganate oxidation method.

The characteristics of these three fractions from acetone and their fatty acid composition are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Fractions obtained by crystallisation of mango seed fat from acetone

	A.		B.		C.	
Wt. (g.)	119.8		77.4		43.6	
Iodine value	35.2		41.4		48.4	
Saponification equivalents	288.4		286.9		285.6	
% Weight	49.8		32.1		18.1	
% Mol.	49.6		32.2		18.2	
Component fatty acids.	% Wt.	% Mol.	% Wt.	% Mol.	% Wt.	% Mol.
Myristic	0.39	0.48	0.56	0.67	1.45	1.77
Palmitic	6.50	7.19	12.36	13.52	9.80	10.68
Stearic	36.86	39.79	34.30	33.81	18.64	18.31
As. arachidic	10.43	9.49	4.05	3.63	1.36	1.21
Oleic	42.83	43.05	48.73	48.37	68.76	68.03

Fully Saturated Glycerides of the Whole fat

30.15 G. of the fat were dissolved in dry acetone (300 c.c.) and on oxidation with powdered potassium permanganate (120 g.) gave 4.6 g. of fully saturated glycerides of S.E. 294.3, A.V. 0.95, and I.V. 0.93. After correcting for acidic matter and residual unsaturated glycerides, it was estimated that the true fully saturated glyceride amounted to 14.57% by weight or 14.2% by mols. The corresponding S.E. of the true fully saturated glycerides would be 293.3, which indicates that they are mostly composed of palmito-stearins. In view of the predominance of stearic acid in the fat and palmitic acid forming a minor component, these fully saturated glycerides can be assumed to be composed of mono-palmito-distearin and tristearin.

From the above data the increments of the component acids in each fraction will be as given in Table V. The different possible groupings of glycerides calculated from the component acids are also included in the table. For these calculations small amounts of myristic acid is included in palmitic acid, while arachidic acid is included in stearic acid.

TABLE V

Composition of fractions A, B and C (Mol. %)

	A.	B.	C.	Total.	Whole fat as determined
Molar proportions of glycerides (%)	49.6	32.2	18.2	100	..
(a) Component fatty acids present (%):					
Myristic	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.7	0.8
Palmitic	3.6	4.4	2.0	10.0	9.7
Stearic	19.7	10.9	3.3	33.9	33.7
As. arachidic	4.7	1.1	0.2	6.0	6.1
Oleic	21.4	15.6	12.4	49.4	49.7
(b) Component glycerides:					
Fully saturated glycerides	14.2	14.2	..
Mono-oleo di-saturated	6.6	17.6	..	24.2	..
Di-oleo mono-saturated	28.8	14.6	17.4	60.8	..
Tri-unsaturated	0.8	0.8	..

With due consideration of the solubility of the different glycerides, the approximate composition of the glycerides present in the various fractions can be estimated. Since the fully saturated glycerides are composed of palmito-stearins, they will be present in fraction A. The di-saturated-mono-unsaturated glycerides being less soluble can be taken as absent in the most soluble fraction C. While di-oleo glycerides being predominating, will be distributed in all the fractions. Tri-olein, if at all present, would be in

TABLE VI

Component glycerides of mango fat

	Fractions			Whole fat (100)
	A (49.6%)	B (32.2%)	C (18.2%)	
Fully saturated glycerides (14.2%)				
Palmito-di-stearin	8.7	8.7
Tri-stearin	5.5	5.5
Mono-oleo glycerides (24.2%)				
Palmito-stearo-olein	2.7	13.8	..	16.5
Di-stearo-olein	3.9	3.8	..	7.7
Di-oleo glycerides (60.8%)				
Palmito-di-olein	6.9	6.9
Stearo-di-olein	28.8	14.6	10.5	53.9
Tri-unsaturated (0.8%)				
Tri-olein	0.8	0.8

fraction C only. The palmitic acid in fractions A and B after accounting for the fully saturated glycerides may be regarded as palmito-stearo-olein. The arachidic acid in fraction A may be arachido-stearo-olein or arachido-di-olein. In fractions B and C, however, it would be present as arachido-di-olein only. Di-saturated glycerides being considered absent in fraction C, there would be small proportion of tri-olein present, after allocating oleic acid for di-oleo glycerides.

The approximate proportions of the various glycerides so estimated will therefore be as given in Table VI.

It will be observed from the above analysis that the glycerides of mango fat do not strictly conform to the "rule of even distribution" in as much as that the fully saturated glycerides content is about 14% although the saturated fatty acids form only about 50% of the mixed acids. Usually, the proportion of the fully saturated glycerides would be insignificant until the saturated acids form 60% of the total mixed acids.

In fatty acid composition mango fat resembles *Vateria Indica* fat (palmitic 10.2, stearic 35.8, arachidic 3.1 and oleic 47.8%. *cf.* Hilditch and Jones, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1931, 51, 468r) to a great extent. Being a solid fat, fairly rich in stearic acid, mango fat would have been very suitable for soap making. But its fat content is so very poor that it is doubtful whether it could be commercially exploited.